

TESTING AND ANALYSIS OF ANISOGRID PREPREG ELEMENT SPECIMEN UNDER UNIAXIAL TENSION AND COMPRESSION

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ABSTRACT

This paper reports on test results and analysis of Anisogrid Prepreg knot and rib specimen under uniaxial tension and compression. Due to the special knot design of the Anisogrid Prepreg structure concept, this investigation aims to characterize stiffness and strength properties for these two kinds of specimen.

Integral Anisogrid structures contain intersecting, integral manufactured ribs with different directions (circumferential, axial, and/or helical) and optionally a load bearing skin. The classical manufacturing method for aerospace grid structures is wet-filament winding. For airframes, an Anisogrid Prepreg structure concept has been developed considering high quality assurance demands and the need of a State of Art manufacturing process (Advanced Fibre Placement). In this investigation, element-sized specimens of this Anisogrid Prepreg structure concept has been analysed and tested. This design concept consists of undisturbed and disturbed Prepreg layers with 60% fibre volume ratio, which are placed in an alternating pattern in the structure. Disturbed layers are cut in the point of intersecting rib directions.

Due to the special stacking of the ribs with rectangular cross-section and very narrow ply widths, a wide reference testing program is used additionally. This means that in the testing program laminate specimens with typical stacking, rib test specimens cut out of a thick plate and manually laid rib and knot specimens have been produced, tested and compared to analytical strength calculations.

As result, an answer is given which stiffness and strength properties in tension and compression can be expected for this Anisogrid Prepreg structure concept.

1 INTRODUCTION

Reaching demands to lightweight design an increased degree of integration is a typical way to reduce assembly effort, weight and costs. Following this philosophy lattice structures are a good example in aerospace applications. The framework of load bearing ribs are manufactured in one shot by wet filament winding, resulting in one piece interstage sections. [1]

This high degree of integration is enabled by ribs, which gets winded with global fibre volume content between 35-40% and over-pressed layers in the knot area of intersecting rib directions. High strength and stiffness properties are a result of this manufacturing process, considering the relatively low fibre volume content.

For structures which highly depend on their stability behaviour, a higher fibre volume ratio can be of higher interest getting highly increased stiffness properties of the laminate. In consequence a Prepreg-Anisogrid design concept with load bearing skin has been invented. The advantage of 60% fibre volume ratio for the global structure only has the drawback of cut plies in the knot area, due to keeping automated fibre placement technology for large scale structures.

For sizing of this structure concept on panel level, stiffness and especially strength properties has to be available. Therefore tests on coupon level have been performed. The question is investigated how much strength and stiffness reduction in the knot area have to be considered, compared to undisturbed ribs.

Whereas standard composite laminates have typically wide in-plane dimensions with much lower thickness. The rib structure instead has very narrow layers but with a high thickness, which

corresponds to the height of the ribs. Preliminary test results showed that the maximum stress in such stacking is lower than theoretically expected. Main reasons are seen in the achieved laminate quality as well as edge effects (the stacking occur by its nature of narrow layers). Therefore two kinds of additional reference specimens have been manufactured and tested. Disturbed and undisturbed specimens have been cut out of a thick plate, achieving a high laminate quality but keeping the edge effects. The second kind of specimen are laminate specimens which have been manufactured and tested as typical laminates with wide in plane dimensions and low thickness, achieving a high laminate quality and reducing possible edge effects.

2 ANISOGRID PREPREG DESIGN CONCEPT

The Anisogrid Prepreg Design Concept consists of helical and circumferential ribs and a load bearing skin, see Figure 1. The ribs are built with rib layers as main load-bearing layers in rib direction and interface layers for an improved connection of the rib structure with the load bearing skin. The rib structure shall be placed fully automatically by fibre placement including the interface layers.

Figure 1: Anisogrid-Prepreg-Design-Concept

The disadvantage of realisable high axial rib stiffness is the absence of possibly over-pressing the rib directions in the knot. Consequently in the current concept, the rib layers of two rib directions have to be cut, so that one layer can run through the knot. This procedure alternates through the knot height for all layers, see Figure 2. Under consideration of three rib directions and an equal distribution of cut and uncut layers in all directions, the concept results in only 33% of uncut layers for each rib direction.

Figure 2: Sequence of cut and uncut layers in Anisogrid-Prepreg-Concept

3 TEST STANDARDS, GEOMETRY, MANUFACTURING AND MATERIAL

Even with the unconventional stacking design of the Anisogrid concept, the stiffness and strength properties was tested according to typical uniaxial testing standards. In consequence similar testing procedure, specimen dimensions and test analysis are used. For the testing of knots, the specimen will be tested uniaxial, pulling or pushing one rib direction, whereas the other rib directions won't be loaded.

For tension, the standard *DIN EN ISO 527-4* is considered, which is used for "Test conditions for isotropic and orthotropic fibre-reinforced plastics" [2]. Considering the manufacturing of the same specimen for tension and compression, the specimen type 2 has been chosen. The testing length of this type 2 is 150 mm plus 50 mm load application elements on each side, resulting in 250 mm specimen length to manufacture. The thickness of the specimen has been determined to 4 mm with respect to the standard. Only the width of the specimen respectively the rib height had to be reduced from the required 25 mm to 18 mm because of tool limitations, see Figure 3 left.

Figure 3: Knot specimen dimension, left: tension, right: compression

For compression, the standard *DIN EN ISO 14126* is considered, which is suitable for unidirectional as well as for multidirectional reinforced plastics, depending on the specimen geometry [3]. For a multidirectional laminate, as it is the case for the rib and knot specimens, the specimen geometry type B2 is recommended. The specimen thickness is also 4 mm and the overall specimen length is 250 mm, see Figure 3. As mentioned for the tension specimen, the width of the compression specimen had also to be reduced to 18 mm, due to tool limitations. Because of the width reduction also the testing length has been reduced to 18 mm, instead of 25 mm according to the standard. This modification of the testing length is necessary in order to prevent buckling.

For monitoring deformations during the test, strain gauges have been used on both sides of the specimen.

The manufacturing of the undisturbed ribs and the knots has been done in a special flat tool with grooves and in a manual laying process. Nine grid knots and six undisturbed rib specimens can be manufactured in one shot in this tool, see Figure 4. The knots have been manufactured with three rib directions, realizing the real staking of the concept in the knot area. The two unloaded directions had to be shortened in length to a certain amount, to fit into the testing devices, see also Figure 3.

Figure 4 : Tool for manufacturing undisturbed grid ribs and grid knots

Due to the tool design and the process of manually placing the layers, the specimen quality in terms of pores and fibre content is acceptable, whether reduced properties had to be expected. In consequence a thick plate has been produced with the same thickness as the height of the manufactured ribs and knots. The specimens out of this thick plate are used as first reference, due to the same geometry but with better laminate quality. The stacking of the thick plate equals the stacking in the Grid rib specimen. In order to realize disturbed plate specimen, which are similar to the grid knots, the same amount of layers have been cut in the middle of the plate. The cut layers in the thick plate have been placed simply face-to-face (see Figure 5 the plate illustration). After curing, the undisturbed (rib) and disturbed (knot simulation) plate specimens have been cut out of the plate with a width of 4 mm, see Figure 5.

Figure 5: Manufactured thick plate and illustrated undisturbed (left) and disturbed (right) plate specimen

Due to the unusual stacking for a composite with very narrow layers but a great thickness, laminate specimens have been manufactured as second reference, see Figure 7. The laminate rib specimens have the same fibre orientation ratio like the Grid rib and undisturbed plate specimen. The laminate knot specimens have the same fibre orientation ratio as it is the case at the weakest point in the knot area, which is described in chapter 4 more in detail.

Figure 6: Manufactured thin plate for laminate rib and knot specimen

As material, the Hexcel HexPly® 8552/AS4 has been used. Achieving a high axial stiffness, a laminate of (66/0/33) has been chosen for the specimen as basic stacking, means in the undisturbed ribs. The stacking in the knot area is different due to the alternating layers of all rib directions, running through the knot. As result, the laminate knot specimen has a fibre orientation ratio of (33/0/66), see chapter 4.

4 ANALYTICAL TESTFORCE PREDICTION

In order to analytically assess the results of the experiments the Classical Laminate Theory is used for the stiffness as well as for stress calculation. As strength criteria the Hashin2D criteria is used with typical differentiation of fibre and matrix failure in each ply. For strength, the different tension and compression modulus are considered in calculation, like given in the data sheet [4]

Following equations are used for fibre failure f_f :

$$\sigma_{11} \geq 0: f_f = \left(\frac{\sigma_1}{X_t}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{S}\right)^2 \quad (1)$$

$$\sigma_{11} < 0: f_f = -\frac{\sigma_1}{X_c} \quad (2)$$

and for matrix failure f_m :

$$\sigma_{22} \geq 0: f_m = \left(\frac{\sigma_{22}}{Y_t}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{12}}{S}\right)^2 \quad (3)$$

$$\sigma_{22} < 0: f_m = \left(\frac{\sigma_{22}}{2S_{23}}\right)^2 + \left[\left(\frac{Y_c}{2S_{23}}\right)^2 - 1\right] \frac{\sigma_{22}}{Y_c} + \left(\frac{\sigma_{12}}{S_{12}}\right)^2 \quad (4)$$

Due to the structure concept with (undisturbed) ribs and knot areas, two material models and theoretical expectations are used. The first model/part is the undisturbed rib section with its laminate stacking between the knots, see Figure 7 green cross-section. The second model/part is the knot area, see Figure 7 beige cross-section. For calculation of the knot area, not the knot stacking itself will be considered but the weakest point, which is seen virtually directly between the rib and the knot. Therefore only the uncut layers get considered with its orientation and all the cut layers are considered as 90° layers.

Figure 7: Material models for analytical analysis

5 TEST RESULTS SUMMARY AND DISCUSSION

Following, the test results for tension and compression will be presented. The results are divided in (undisturbed) rib results and knot (respectively disturbed rib) results. For comparison, the test results are related to the expected analytical calculation.

At least four but mostly six specimens have been tested to get one property value shown below.

5.1 Tension

Diagram 1 shows the results for the tension modulus:

Diagram 1: Analysis (green) and test results for tension modulus;
 left: rib laminate (blue), undisturbed plate (red), Grid rib specimen (violet);
 right: knot laminate (blue), disturbed plate (red), Grid knot specimen (violet).

As result of the analytical analyses, a tension modulus of 98 GPa has been calculated for the rib stacking (66/0/33). The test results of all rib specimens are, as expected, lower but within a range of 93% and 87% of the analytical reference. The Grid rib specimens have the lowest tension modulus. As result for the knot laminate stacking (33/0/66), a tension modulus of 54GPa has been calculated, see Diagram 1 right. The test results for the knot specimens are in contrast to the rib results quite different. The knot laminate specimens have on average an about 7 % lower modulus than calculated, whether it

is the same reduction than for the rib laminate specimens. On the one hand it is questionable why such reduction occurs, on the other hand it seems to be from inspiring confidence that both laminates has the same reduction. The results for the disturbed plate and the Grid knot specimens are on the first look surprisingly good, because they are 61% and 55% higher than the calculated expected value, see Diagram 1 right. On the other hand it can be seen, that the values of the knot specimens reached nearly exactly the modulus of the undisturbed plate and Grid rib specimens.

Overall it has been showed, that the small knot area with varying laminate stacking is not influencing the stiffness of the knot specimens in tension. As result, the stiffness value of the undisturbed rib can be used for the whole rib structure for sizing Even if the local laminate stacking is different.

Diagram 2 shows the results for the maximum tension strength for the analysis and test specimens:

Diagram 2: Analysis (green) and test results for tension strength;
left: rib laminate (blue), undisturbed plate (red), Grid rib specimen (violet);
right: knot laminate (blue), disturbed plate (red), Grid knot specimen (violet).

As result of the analytical analyses, the fibre failure occurs in the rib laminate at ca. 1500 MPa. The test results for all rib specimens were remarkable lower with a range between 83% and 76%. The Grid rib specimens have again the lowest maximum tension stress of approx. 1150 MPa. As result for the knot laminate stacking (33/0/66) fibre failure should occur at 830 MPa, see Diagram 2. The knot laminate specimens reached nearly the same reduction in calculated maximum strength as the rib laminate specimens with 82%. On the one hand, this is a remarkable reduction. On the other hand it is again interesting, that both laminate test results are reduced in the same amount. A massive reduction of maximum tension strength has been achieved for the disturbed plate specimens and the Grid knot specimens. In comparison to the modulus it is an even higher reduction compared to the knot laminate specimens. The disturbed plate and knot specimens ~~got~~ have nearly the same maximum tension strength of ca. 400 MPa. Compared to the Grid rib specimens a strength reduction to 34% occurs. Considering the 33% of cut layers in the knot area, the reduction seems to correlate simply to this amount.

Consequently as expected, a strong reduction of tension strength for the knot has been seen at testing and has to be considered in sizing processes.

5.2 Compression

Diagram 3 shows the results for the compression modulus:

Diagram 3: Analysis (green) and test results for compression modulus; left: rib laminate (blue), undisturbed plate (red), Grid rib specimen (violet); right: knot laminate (blue), disturbed plate (red), Grid knot specimen (violet).

According to the analytical analysis, a compression modulus of 89 GPa has been calculated for the rib stacking (66/0/33) and 50 GPa for the knot laminate stacking (33/0/66). Similar to tension, the test results for all rib specimens were slightly lower within a range of 92% and 89% of the analytical reference. Also the test results for the knot specimens show the same trends. The knot laminate specimens have the same lower modulus as the rib laminate specimens with 93%. The results for the disturbed plate and the Grid knot specimens have also nearly exactly the modulus of the undisturbed plate and Grid rib specimens.

Similar to the tension results, it can be concluded, that the small knot area with varying laminate stacking is not influencing the stiffness in compression of the knot specimens. As result, the stiffness value of the undisturbed rib can be used for the whole rib structure for sizing processes.

Diagram 4 show the results for the maximum compression strength:

Diagram 4: Analysis (green) and test results for compression strength;
left: rib laminate (blue), undisturbed plate (red), Grid rib specimen (violet);
right: knot laminate (blue), disturbed plate (red), Grid knot specimen (violet).

As result of the analytical analyses, the fibre failure shall occur in the rib laminate at ca. 1050 MPa. The test results for all rib specimens were lower with a range between 94% and 79%, whereas the reduction is lower than at tension. As result for the knot laminate stacking (33/0/66) fibre failure was calculated at ca. 590 MPa. The knot laminate specimens reached a slightly higher maximum strength. An even higher maximum stress reached the disturbed plate specimens. Compared to the knot laminate expectation it seems to be surprising, on the other hand it is compared to the undisturbed plate specimens still a reduction to ca. 75%. It seems that the cut layers are not as bad for compression as for tension (reduction to ca. 30%). A still high reduction of maximum compression strength has been achieved for the Grid knot specimens. Compared to the Grid rib specimens a strength reduction to ca. 50% occurs. This reduction is also lower than for tension (reduction to ca. 34%).

Consequently also for compression a high reduction of maximum strength has been seen, but the reduction is not as high as for tension. However, a consideration to sizing processes still has to be done.

6 CONCLUSION

For the specific Anisogrid-Prepreg Design Concept, static tension and compression tests have been performed and strength and stiffness results have been compared. The goal was to determine the reduction of grid knot specimens compared to undisturbed Grid rib specimens.

Therefore a high amount of undisturbed rib and knot specimens have been manufactured as well as additional kinds of reference specimens. For a better understanding of effects, typical laminate specimens have been produced with the same rib and knot fibre orientation ratio. Second undisturbed and disturbed rib specimens have been investigated, which have been cut out of a thick plate. Overall 65 specimens have been produced and tested.

Resultant the tests show, that the stiffness of the undisturbed rib (rib between knots) can be used for sizing for the whole rib structure including knot areas. The resulting different stacking in the knot area showed no remarkable influence to the stiffness for tension as well as for compression. In consequence the advantage of achievable high stiffness can be fully used for the Anisogrid Prepreg concept. This

can be exploited especially for stiffened structures, where stability is a more critical design driver than strength.

In terms of strength, the Anisogrid Prepreg concept has to operate with much lower maximum allowable stresses for the knot area. Compared to the undisturbed rib, the reduction to circa 34% in tension and even 50% in compression is massive. The cut plies in the knot area are failing very early and because of the very narrow ply widths, cracks seem to separate the layers directly from side to side. In consequence the load bearing cross-section gets reduced very quickly.

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